

Metabolically engineered *Klebsiella oxytoca* KMS004 by deletion of *pyruvate formate-lyase B (pflB)*

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Abstract

Klebsiella oxytoca KMS004 is a metabolically engineered strain originally developed to enhance D-lactate production by eliminating ethanol- and acetate-producing pathways. In this study, we further improved the strain by deleting the *pyruvate formate-lyase B (pflB)* gene, which is responsible for formate production, a metabolite that readily converts into carbon dioxide and water during fermentation. The *pflB* gene was deleted using homologous recombination with a kanamycin resistance cassette. The genetic modification was confirmed through PCR and agarose gel electrophoresis, demonstrating successful replacement of *pflB* with the antibiotic resistance marker. The engineered strain (*K. oxytoca* KMS004 $\Delta pflB$) can potentially improve D-lactate production by redirecting carbon flux away from formate formation. Future work will focus on removing the antibiotic resistance gene and optimizing fermentation conditions. This study highlights the potential of genetic engineering to enhance microbial production efficiency and provides a foundation for further metabolic modifications using advanced gene-editing tools such as CRISPR-Cas9.

Keywords: *Klebsiella oxytoca* KMS004; Metabolically engineered; Deletion; Formate

1. Introduction

Metabolic engineering has emerged as a powerful tool for optimizing microbial strains to enhance the production of industrially valuable compounds. *Klebsiella oxytoca* is a facultative anaerobic bacterium known for its diverse metabolic capabilities, including the production of D-lactate, 1,3-propanediol, 2,3-butanediol, acetate, ethanol, succinate, and formate (Jantama et al., 2015). Given the increasing demand for D-lactate as a precursor for biodegradable polylactic acid (PLA), metabolic engineering approaches have been applied to redirect carbon flux towards D-lactate biosynthesis while minimizing the formation of unwanted by-products (Sangproo et al., 2012). *Klebsiella oxytoca* KMS004 is an engineered strain developed by Sangproo (2012) through the deletion of key metabolic genes, including *adhE* (alcohol dehydrogenase) and *pta-ackA* (phosphotransacetylase-acetate kinase A), from the wild-type strain. These deletions effectively reduced ethanol and acetate production, leading to a higher D-lactate yield compared to the parent strain (In et al., 2020). However, despite these improvements, *K. oxytoca* KMS004 still produces formate, a by-product of anaerobic metabolism. The *pyruvate formate-lyase B (pflB)* enzyme catalyzes the conversion of pyruvate to formate and acetyl-CoA, a key intermediate in central metabolism. Since formate is unstable under fermentation conditions and decomposes into carbon dioxide and water, its production represents a carbon loss that could otherwise contribute to D-lactate synthesis (Zhou et al., 2006). Previous studies have demonstrated that deleting *pflB* in various microbial strains can enhance the efficiency of desired fermentation pathways.

For example, the deletion of *pflB* in *Escherichia coli* significantly reduced formate accumulation and improved lactate production (Datsenko & Wanner, 2000; Grabar et al., 2006). Similarly, metabolic engineering of *K. oxytoca* has shown that eliminating competing pathways can improve yields of targeted metabolites (Jantama et al., 2015). These findings suggest that the deletion of *pflB* in *K. oxytoca* KMS004 could enhance D-lactate production by minimizing formate-associated carbon loss.

The objective of this study is to genetically modify *K. oxytoca* KMS004 by deleting the *pflB* gene, thereby redirecting metabolic flux from formate production toward D-lactate biosynthesis. The gene deletion was performed using homologous recombination, with a kanamycin resistance gene serving as a selectable marker. The modified strain was validated through PCR and agarose gel electrophoresis. This study provides a foundation for further metabolic engineering strategies to optimize fermentation efficiency and industrial-scale D-lactate production.

2. Materials and Methods

1. Strains, media, and growth condition

Bacterial strains, plasmids, and primers are listed in **Table 1**. *K. oxytoca* KMS004 was provided by Metabolic bioprocess engineering laboratory (Sangproo, 2012). Culture will be grown at 37 °C, 200 rpm in Luria-Bertani (LB) broth containing 10 g of peptone, 5 g of yeast extraction, and 5 g of sodium chloride per 1 liter of DI water. Cultures will be also maintained on solid medium of agar (20 g/L agar). Apramycin (50 µg/mL) and kanamycin (50 µg/mL) were included as appropriate.

2. Genetically engineering method

DNA amplification by polymerase chain reaction (PCR)

The standard PCR was performed using 10x PCR master mix solution in a PCR of 50 µL. 50 µL of master mix containing 10 mM of each dNTP (dATP, dGTP, dCTP and dTTP), PCR buffer (20 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.8, 10 mM KCl, 10 mM (NH₄)₂SO₄, 2 mM MgSO₄, 1% (v/v) Triton X-100, 1 mg/mL nuclease-free BSA, and *Tag* polymerase enzyme), 40 pmole of each primer (forward and reverse strand primers), 50 ng of either plasmid or chromosomal DNA template and distilled water, will be added to the mixer. The reaction was performed in automated Flexcyler PCR machine (Analytikjena, Germany). The PCR condition is shown in Table 2. After the amplification reaction is finished, an aliquot of the PCR mixture was examined on 1% (w/v) agarose gel electrophoresis.

Agarose gel electrophoresis of DNA

To analyze the size of DNA fragments, the PCR products, and DNA fragment was subjected to agarose gel electrophoresis. The appropriate amount of agarose powder was dissolved in 0.5x TBE buffer [89 mM Tris-HC, 89mM boric acid, 25 mM EDTA pH8.0] or 1x TAE buffer [40 mM Tris-HCl, 40 mM acetic acid, 25 mM EDTA pH 8.0] under boiling temperature to ensure the homogeneity of the gel solution. 6 µL of loading dye [0.1% (w/v) bromophenol blue, 40% (w/v) Ficoll and 5 mM EDTA] were added and mixed well to the DNA samples before loading into the wells of the solidified gel. The electrophoresis was performed at a constant voltage, 100 V, for 30 min. After completion of electrophoresis, the gel was taken to check DNA bands. DNA bands were shown by visualized under UV light and photographed by a gel documentation system.

Table 1. Strains, plasmids, and primers used in this study

Strains	Relevant characteristics	References
KMS004	<i>K. oxytoca</i> ($\Delta adhE$, $\Delta pta-ackA$)	(Sangproo et al. 2012)
KMS004	KMS004 ($\Delta pflB$)	This study
Plasmids		
pKD4	<i>bla</i> FRT- <i>kan</i> -FRT	(Datsenko & Wanner, 2000)
pLOI3420	<i>acc</i> γ β <i>exo</i> (Red recombinase), temperature-conditional replicon	Wood et al. (2005)
Primers		
	Sequence	
<i>pflB-kan-F</i>	5' atgtccgagc ttaatgaaa gtagccaca gcctgggaag gttt <u>aaatcactggatataccacc</u> 3'	This study
<i>pflB-kan-R</i>	5' ttacatggtc tgagtgaagg tacgagtaat cacgtcctgc tgctg <u>ccagcgcgtttatttgta</u> 3'	This study

Underlined 20 bp are represented for kanamycin gene

Table 2. PCR parameters for the amplification of specific genes

PCR profile to amplify gene				
Step	Period	Temperature (°C)	Time	Number of cycles
1	Pre-denaturing	95	9 min	1
	Denaturing	95	30 s	
2	Annealing	55	30 s	35
	Extension	72	2 min	
3	Extra-extension	72	10 min	1

PCR Purification

QIAquick PCR Purification Kit Protocol was applied to purify PCR product

- Add 5 volumes of buffer PB (contain pH indicator) to 1 volume of PCR sample and mix
- Place a QIAquick spin column in a provided 2 ml collection tube
- To bind DNA, apply the sample to the QIAquick column and centrifuge for 30-60s
- Discard flow-through. Place the QIAquick column back into the same tube
- To wash, add 0.75 ml Buffer PE to the QIAquick column and centrifuge 30-60s
- Discard flow-through and place the QIAquick column back in the same tube. Centrifuge the column for an additional 1 min
- Place QIAquick column in a clean 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tube.
- To elute DNA, add 50 μ l Buffer EB (10 mM Tris·Cl, pH 8.5) or water (pH 7.0–8.5) to the center of the QIAquick membrane and centrifuge the column for 1 min. Alternatively, for increased DNA concentration, add 30 μ l elution buffer to the center of the QIAquick membrane, let the column stand for 1 min, and then centrifuge

Preparation of *K. oxytoca* KMS004 competent cell

A single colony of *K. oxytoca* KMS004 was inoculated into 3 mL of LB broth and incubated at 37°C with shaking 200 rpm until reaching the OD₅₅₀ nm in the range 0.3-0.5. The culture was centrifuged at 4000 rpm, 4°C for 7 min. The cell pellet was re-suspended and washed in 4.5 mL of ice-cold de-ionized water for 2 times, in 2 mL of ice-cold de-ionized water for 1 times and in 2 mL of ice-cold 15% glycerol for 1 time. After washing the cell, the white cell pellet was resuspended in 1 mL of sterile ice-cold 15% glycerol and placed on ice for 10 min until used.

Transformation of *K. oxytoca* KMS004 by electroporation

PCR fragment products 100 μ L was mixed with electroporated competent cells 200 μ L, and the mixture was transferred to an ice-cold 0.4 cm electroporation cuvette. The cuvette was incubated on ice for 5 min. The cells were pulsed by using electroporator (Bio-Rad MicroPulser™, USA) under the conditions used with *K. oxytoca* KMS004 (2500 V, pulse length 5 ms, *Eco*R2). Then 1000 μ L of LB broth was added to the cuvette immediately and the solution was transferred to a sterile 15 mL flask. The flask was incubated at 30 °C with 150 rpm shaking for 2 h. transformed cells, 200 μ L, was spread on LB agar plates containing suitable antibiotics depending on antibiotic-resistant gene harbored in the DNA fragments and was incubated overnight at 37 °C.

Deletion of *pflB* gene in *K. oxytoca* KMS004

Plasmids and primers used in this study are summarized in **Table 1**. Methods for chromosomal deletions, integration, and removal of antibiotic resistance genes have been described in ((Datsenko & Wanner, 2000; Grabar, Zhou, Shanmugam, Yomano, & Ingram, 2006; Posfai, Koob, Kirkpatrick, & R., 1997; Zhou, Grabar, Shanmugam, & Ingram, 2006). Sense primers contain sequences corresponding to the N-terminus of each targeted gene followed by 20 bp (underlined) corresponding to the FRT-*kan*-FRT cassette. The anti-sense primer contains sequences corresponding to the C-terminal region of each targeted gene followed by 20 bp (underlined) corresponding to the cassette. The FRT-*kan*-FRT was amplified by PCR using these primers and pKD4 as the template. Amplified DNA fragments were electroporated into *K. Oxytoca* KMS004 harboring *Red recombinase* (pLOI3420). In resulting recombinants, the FRT-*kan*-FRT cassette was replaced the deleted region of the target gene by homologous recombination.

3. Result and Discussion

1. Confirmation of *pflB* gene deletion

Fig1. Marker for comparing to the samples

Fig.2. Kanamycin fragment using pKD4 as a template, and primer-km-R, F (R = reverse, F = forward)

Fig.3. pKD4 plasmid containing 1.5 kbp

To verify the deletion of the *pyruvate formate-lyase B* (*pflB*) gene in *K. oxytoca* KMS004, PCR amplification was performed using specific primers targeting the disrupted region. Agarose gel electrophoresis of the PCR products showed a distinct DNA band of approximately 1.5 kb, corresponding to the kanamycin resistance gene (*kanR*) inserted in place of *pflB* (**Fig.2**). The successful amplification of the expected band size confirms the replacement of *pflB* with *kanR* through homologous recombination. Similar results have been reported in previous studies where homologous recombination was used to delete competing metabolic pathways in *K. oxytoca* and *Escherichia coli* to enhance targeted metabolite production (Datsenko & Wanner, 2000; Jantama et al., 2015).

2. PCR product using KMS004 as template

Homologous recombination technique was applied in transformation of competent cells to knockout *pflB* gene from chromosome of *K. oxytoca* KMS004 replace by kanamycin resistance gene. To claim that kanamycin is replaced into chromosome sequences by running PCR. KMS004 was used as DNA template. Compare result between marker and sample were revealed that the band is contained about 1.5 kbp (**Fig.4**). Depending on the band, kanamycin genomes is already replaced in chromosome sequences.

Fig.4. Comparison between marker and sample used cells as template and primer-F, R

3. Transformation of competent cells

Fig.5. *K. oxytoca* KMS004 restrict on **A:** agar plate (apramycin), and **B:** agar late (kanamycin)

KMS004 is a strain resistance to apramycin which can grow on an agar plate containing apramycin (**Fig.5A**). Only KMS004 strains were grown on the plate. After applied the homologous recombination to knockout *pflB* of chromosome genome of KMS004 strains and replaced by kanamycin resistance gene, restrict plate on agar containing kanamycin was applied to select only strains of interest (**Fig. 5B**). As the result of the strict plate, colonies were grown which indicated that KMS004 containing kanamycin and deflection of *pflB* were achieved. To further confirm the deletion of *pflB*, transformed *K. oxytoca* KMS004 strains were plated on selective media containing kanamycin. The presence of colony growth (Figure 5B) indicates that only recombinant strains carrying the kanR marker successfully survived, further verifying the replacement of *pflB*. This selection strategy ensures that the engineered strain no longer produces formate, which is expected to improve carbon flux toward D-lactate production. Previous studies have demonstrated that eliminating *pflB* can significantly reduce formate accumulation, leading to a redirection of metabolic flux towards more desirable fermentation products (Grabar et al., 2006; Zhou et al., 2006).

4. Implication for D-lactate production

The deletion of *pflB* is expected to enhance D-lactate production by reducing carbon loss associated with formate formation. Formate is an unstable by-product that decomposes into carbon dioxide and water, representing a metabolic inefficiency in lactate-producing strains. By eliminating *pflB*, more pyruvate can be directed toward lactate biosynthesis, potentially increasing the overall yield. A similar metabolic engineering strategy has been applied in *E. coli*, where knocking out *pflB* significantly improved D-lactate productivity by minimizing carbon loss (Datsenko & Wanner, 2000). However, it is important to consider potential metabolic trade-offs. The removal of *pflB* could lead to an increased reliance on alternative pathways for acetyl-CoA production, which may impact overall strain fitness. Future studies should focus on evaluating the fermentation performance of the mutant strain under controlled conditions to quantify improvements in D-lactate yield. Additionally, since the current deletion method introduced a kanamycin resistance marker, further work is needed to remove the *kanR* gene using FLP recombinase to create a marker-free strain suitable for industrial application.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, these experiments and data could be used to apply for the gene deletion. All experiments were claimed to show the achievement before further steps. Thus, metabolically engineering of KMS004 by eliminating *pflB* gene is done successfully. In this case, kanamycin gene is still present in strains which should be removed. By using pFT-A vector harbored FLP recombinase could be removed kanamycin gene. After removing antibiotic gene, the strain would be applied in industrial. Similarly, after selected research course, I know and understand more in the laboratory include using PCR, Agarose gel electrophoresis, PCR purification, prepare competent cells, the transformation of KMS004. All steps of engineered strains have to pay attention, concentration and care about hygiene during the performance. On the other hand, a modern method is called CRISPR/Cas9, is more effective to knockout gene. So that, if we compare between homologous recombination technique (HR) and CRISPR/Cas9 methods, we can estimate that HR technique is expensed lower than CRISPR/Cas9 but less efficiency than CRISPR/Cas9. According to the rate of efficiency, CRISPR/Cas9 should be applied to engineer strains for next experiment.

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Compliance with ethical standards

Conflict of interest: The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Data availability statement: All data from this research study are available from the corresponding author.

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